

QUESTIONNAIRE FOR THE INVESTIGATION OF CANINE BRUCELLOSIS IN THE FRENCH KENNELS.

Date	Kennel contact details	Who has completed the questionnaire

PART 1: Kennel

<i>The premises</i>		
QUESTION	ANSWER	ADDITIONAL INFORMATION
1. How many dogs are present in the kennel?		
2. Have new dogs been introduced within the last year? Have these animals been imported from abroad?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	Specify the origin of introduced animals
3. Are there one (or more) production animal farms in the vicinity of the kennel?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	If Yes: <input type="checkbox"/> bovines <input type="checkbox"/> goats <input type="checkbox"/> sheep <input type="checkbox"/> pigs Other:
4. Is the maternity isolated?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Boxes <input type="checkbox"/> booths <input type="checkbox"/> Other:
5. Is there space dedicated to adult dogs?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Boxes <input type="checkbox"/> Isolated courtyards <input type="checkbox"/> Commune courtyard <input type="checkbox"/> Parcs <input type="checkbox"/> Nesting spaces <input type="checkbox"/> Others: (specify)
6. Are there relaxation areas?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Isolated courtyards <input type="checkbox"/> Commune courtyard <input type="checkbox"/> Parcs
7. Are there spaces dedicated for reproduction?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	
8. Is there a dedicated quarantine?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Boxes <input type="checkbox"/> Isolated courtyards
9. Other activities	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Boarding <input type="checkbox"/> Grooming <input type="checkbox"/> Education/training/agility <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)
10. Have dogs been participating in the dogs shows/ beauty contests?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> In France <input type="checkbox"/> abroad

Free comments:

Reproduction

1. Reproduction method	<input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input type="checkbox"/> In vitro	Semen: <input type="checkbox"/> Fresh <input type="checkbox"/> cooled <input type="checkbox"/> Frozen
2. Standardisation	<input type="checkbox"/> Internal <input type="checkbox"/> External	State how many internal standardizations
3. How many reproduction females are there?		
4. Semen examination	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Regular Frequency: <input type="checkbox"/> Before every reproduction <input type="checkbox"/> Only before IV <input type="checkbox"/> In the case of infertility
5. Have there been any symptoms of disease in the male reproductive organs?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Prostatitis <input type="checkbox"/> Orchitis
6. Testing for infectious diseases: Brucellosis	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Serological tests (blood) <input type="checkbox"/> Tests on various tissues (organs, unborn puppies, placenta, LCR) <input type="checkbox"/> tests on bodily fluids (sperm, urine...)
7. Have there been infertility problems within the last year?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	Specify <input type="checkbox"/> smaller litters <input type="checkbox"/> no puppies
8. Have there been cases of stopped gestation (fetal resorption < 40 days) with the last year?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	
9. Have there been miscarriages (>40 days) within the last year?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	
10. Have there been cases of neonatal mortality within the last year?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Stillbirth <input type="checkbox"/> Early (< 48h) <input type="checkbox"/> Late (2-21 days)
11. Have there been problems in locomotion in some dogs?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> lameness <input type="checkbox"/> muscular weakness <input type="checkbox"/> discospondylite
12. How many mattings there are per year? (or last year)		
How many litters there are per year? (or last year)		

Free comments:

PART 2 Biosafety

<i>Prevention</i>		
1. Systemic Quarantine for every new arriving animal	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> < 7d <input type="checkbox"/> between 7 and 14 days <input type="checkbox"/> > 14d
2. Is moving only forward strategy implemented in the whole kennel?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	
3. Is there dedicated material and equipment for each sector of the kennel?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	
4. Does personnel uses systematically protection equipment when working with delivery material (tissues, placentas, miscarried fetuses)?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Gloves <input type="checkbox"/> Overshoes <input type="checkbox"/> Blouses <input type="checkbox"/> Visors <input type="checkbox"/> Single use <input type="checkbox"/> Reusable <input type="checkbox"/> Others:
5. Do you know canine brucellosis?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	
6. Are you aware of brucellosis zoonotic potential?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	
7. Management of miscarried fetuses and stillbirths	<input type="checkbox"/> Internal <input type="checkbox"/> External	<input type="checkbox"/> Burying <input type="checkbox"/> Elimination by specialized company <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)
8. Origin of water, used for dogs to drink?		<input type="checkbox"/> Well <input type="checkbox"/> Communal water source <input type="checkbox"/> Rain water collectors <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)
9. Is it possible for animals to come in contact with waste water?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	
10. Cleaning and disinfection done in a separate manner (first cleaning and then disinfection)?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> in the same bucket <input type="checkbox"/> Two in one products <input type="checkbox"/> systemic rincing in the clear water before disinfection
11. Usually used disinfectants		<input type="checkbox"/> Quaternary ammoniums <input type="checkbox"/> Bleach <input type="checkbox"/> Glutaraldehydes <input type="checkbox"/> Other Specify the frequency these are being used: <input type="checkbox"/> Once per day <input type="checkbox"/> 1-2 times per week <input type="checkbox"/> 1-2 times per month

PART 3 Sampled animals

Please fill-in the Part 3 for each sampled animal

Medical history		
1. Electronic chip number		
2. Breed		
3. Birth date		Sex <input type="checkbox"/> F <input type="checkbox"/> M
4. Has this animal been born in this kennel?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	If imported, specify the country of origin:
5. Has animal been used for reproduction?	<input type="checkbox"/> Oui <input type="checkbox"/> No	Si oui, préciser date dernière saillie + identification partenaire de saillie :
6. Any symptoms of infertility?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> I don't know	<input type="checkbox"/> reduced litter size <input type="checkbox"/> females without pups
7. History of embryo resorption (< 40 days)?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> I don't know	Specify
8. History of miscarriage (>40 days) ?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> I don't know	Specify
9. Infectious diseases testing?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	Specify <input type="checkbox"/> Brucellosis <input type="checkbox"/> Herpesvirus <input type="checkbox"/> Vaginal bacteriology

Free comments: